

Time measurement in inertial coordinate systems.

Abstract.

The determination of the rate of the passage of time based on the results of the Michelson-Morley experiment in the inertial coordinate systems (x, y, z, t).

In the paper [1] a condition has been formulated for the simultaneity of events occurring in the inertial systems of reference moving relative to each other in a vacuum with a uniform rectilinear motion at a constant speed v .

This condition implies that a light ray emitted from the point A, which is the origin of a stationary system of reference (x, y, z, t) takes exactly the same time to reach the point B, which is the origin of a moving system of reference (x', y', z', t') moving in space rectilinearly at a constant speed v relative to the stationary system, as a light ray sent at the same time in the opposite direction from the point B to the point A.

This condition derives directly from the experiment conducted by Michelson-Morley in 1887 in a laboratory in Cleveland (USA), which has been repeated many times throughout the year during the Earth's movement around the Sun, and therefore in a situation where the speed of the laboratory in space oscillated between 29.3 km/s (at aphelion) - 30.3 km/s (at perihelion). The Michelson-Morley experiment has also been repeatedly conducted in other laboratories around the world, yielding the same result, namely that the speed of visible light, i.e. electromagnetic rays in the range from 380 nm (violet) to 780 nm (red), is independent of whether they are emitted from a stationary or moving light source.

The results of this experiment have led the author of the paper [1] to formulate a conclusion, which he has formulated in the following equation:

$$t_B - t_A = t'_A - t_B \quad (1)$$

where:

t_A - the reading on the clock in the stationary coordinate system A (x, y, z, t) at the moment of sending a light pulse from A to B

t_B - the reading on the clock in the moving coordinate system B (x', y', z', t') at the moment of arrival of a light pulse from A to B

t'_A - the reading on the clock in the stationary coordinate system A (x, y, z, t) at the moment of return of a light pulse from B to A

By multiplying the left and right sides of the above equation (1) by the speed of light c , we obtain the values of the distance between the origins of the systems of reference. They are identical $AB=BA$ at any given moment (t) despite the fact that the moving system of reference B is moving away from the stationary system of reference along the straight line connecting them at the constant speed v .

In each of the coordinate systems (A and B), there is an identical clock counting the passage of time in a given system. The readings from the clock in the stationary system A can be transposed from A to B at the speed 'c' along the path AB, and conversely, the readings from B to A can be transposed from B

to A along the same path, but in the opposite direction BA, also at the speed 'c'. The transmission of readings along the same path AB=BA takes place simultaneously but in the opposite directions and at the same speed 'c'. If the clock A sends the first pulse towards B, and the clock in B sends the first pulse towards the clock A at the same time, there will be a full correlation of the readings of both clocks, with some unknown time setting on the clock A and on the clock B. Due to the fact that the clocks in both systems are identical, we can, for example, after 15 minutes have passed in the system A, send another pulse towards B and repeat the whole situation. From the identical clock B (indistinguishable from the clock A), simultaneously with the second pulse sent from A to B, a second pulse is sent from B to A, and again we obtain full correlation of the readings, but 15 minutes after obtaining the first correlation. The time interval between the first pulse sent from A to B and the second pulse sent from A to B after 15 minutes will correspond to the time interval between the first and second pulses sent from the clock B to A at the same time, also amounting to 15 minutes. An identical clock must measure an identical time. In this way, it is possible to correlate any time intervals passing in both coordinate systems, which proves that time flows at the same speed in both coordinate systems under consideration [2].

Instead of a light pulse, any electromagnetic wave of any frequency can be used to transpose the signal, because, as is now commonly known, all electromagnetic waves, regardless of frequency, travel at the same speed 'c' in a vacuum.

This fact means that transformations describing changes in the coordinates from the stationary system A (x, y, z, t) to the moving system B (x', y', z', t') and conversely are the Galilean transformations.

Summary.

The speed of the passing time in the stationary and moving inertial systems is thus the same, as presented in the paper [2].

Bibliography.

[1] Albert Einstein, *Annalen der Physik* 17, (1905), p.891

[2] Andrzej Kidawa, *Journal of Advance Research in Mathematics and Statistic*, vol.12, Issue 1, Dec2025. p.26